

SEARCH FOR NEW INSECTICIDES. PART I

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o-Hydroxyketones of five esters of 2-bromo-4-*tert.*-butylphenol have been prepared by the Fries rearrangement and converted into their allyl ethers with a view to studying their insecticidal activity.

A good contact insecticide must have a combination of a toxic and a lipid-soluble groupings in its molecule (Lauger *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1944, 27, 918). The toxic groupings can be obtained by introducing the residues of inhalation narcotics into the insect poisonous components. Validity of this hypothesis was justified by Lauger *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), who showed that allyloxy-aryl ethers were good contact insecticides. Keeping this in view, we have prepared five compounds containing allyl groups as toxophores and the ether linkage having lipophilic properties (cf. Chen and Sumerford, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4694). These compounds also contain a ketonic group which would increase the lipid solubility and may further enhance their insecticidal activity.

Five esters of 2-bromo-4-*tert.*-butylphenol, viz., acetate, propionate, butyrate, caproate and heptoate, were obtained by the action of the appropriate acid chloride on the phenol. The Fries rearrangement of these esters was studied at 110° without a solvent.

In all the cases studied, *o*-hydroxyketones were obtained, exhibiting red coloration with 1% ferric chloride solution, and forming yellow crystalline solids with dilute 2% caustic soda solution (cf. Pyman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 280).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The esters of 2-bromo-4-*tert.*-butylphenol, prepared by the method of Spasov, described earlier (Sen and Tiwari, this *Journal*, 1932, 29, 358), are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

2-Bromo-4- <i>tert.</i> -butyl-phenyl esters.	Yield.	B. P.	Mol. formula	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Acetate	97%	120°/8 mm	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₄ Br	52.92	53.14	5.52	5.54
Propionate	93	128°/3	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₄ Br	54.46	54.74	5.93	5.97
Butyrate	80	148°/2	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ O ₄ Br	55.95	56.18	6.32	6.35
Caproate	96	145°/2	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₄ Br	59.11	59.34	6.91	6.93
Heptoate	98	148°/2	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ O ₄ Br	59.61	59.81	7.30	7.33

The Fries Rearrangement of the Esters: Rearrangement at 110°.—The ester (0.1M) was rearranged by keeping it with anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.15M) at 110° for 2 hours. The hydroxyketones were isolated, purified and characterised in the usual way (Table II). The method has been described by Sen and Tiwari (*loc. cit.*). The *o*-hydroxyketones obtained by the Fries rearrangement of these esters were converted into their allyl ethers. These were characterised through their 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones. The work on the insecticidal activity of these compounds is in progress.

TABLE II

Bromo-4- <i>tert</i> -butyl-phenyl esters.	Ketone formed.	Yield.	B.P.	K e t o n e s		2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones.		% Nitrogen.	
				% Carbon Found.	% Hydrogen Found	M.P.	Mol. Formula.	Found.	Calc.
Acetate	R-methyl-K	54%	142°/3 mm	53.14	5.51	200°	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ Br	12.39	12.41
Propionate	R-ethyl-K	68	165°/3	54.51	5.94	225°	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₄ Br	11.91	12.04
Butyrate	R- <i>n</i> -propyl-K	65	150°/2	55.94	6.34	175°	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₄ Br	11.39	11.69
Caproate	R- <i>n</i> -amyl-K	68	210°/9	59.03	6.93	136°	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ O ₂ N ₄ Br	11.03	11.05
Heptate	R- <i>n</i> -hexyl-K	65	200°/2	59.43	7.30	140-41°	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₄ Br	10.59	10.75

K = ketone; R = 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-*tert*-butylphenyl.

N.B. The molecular formula of the ketone is the same as of the ester.

TABLE III

Hydroxy-ketone.	Ether formed.	Yield.	B.P.	Mol. formula.	R e t e r s.		2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones.					
					% Carbon Found	% Hydrogen Found	Mol. formula.	M.P.	Found.	Calc.		
R-methyl-K	R'-methyl-K	66%	115°/1 mm	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ Br	57.65	57.88	6.20	6.11	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₄ Br	165°	11.30	11.53
R-ethyl-K	R'-ethyl-K	65	135°/1	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₂ Br	59.01	59.07	6.43	6.46	C ₂₃ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₄ Br	157°	10.64	11.09
R- <i>n</i> -propyl-K	R'- <i>n</i> -propyl-K	56	195°/16	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ O ₂ Br	59.97	60.17	6.77	6.78	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₄ Br	130°	10.45	10.79
R- <i>n</i> -amyl-K	R'- <i>n</i> -amyl-K	76	165°/1	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ O ₂ Br	61.95	62.11	7.20	7.39	C ₂₆ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₄ Br	129°	10.11	10.26
R- <i>n</i> -hexyl-K	R'- <i>n</i> -heptyl-K	68	164°/1	C ₂₀ H ₂₈ O ₂ Br	64.09	64.30	7.33	7.34	...	...	...	...

K = ketone.

R = 2-Hydroxy-3-bromo-5-*tert*-butylphenyl.

R' = 2-Allyloxy-3-bromo-5-*tert*-butylphenyl.

N.B. 3-Allyloxy-3-bromo-5-*tert*-butylphenyl-hydrazones has not formed.

Allyl-aryl Ethers.—A mixture of allyl bromide (0.11M), freshly fused potassium carbonate (0.15M) and 80 c.c. of anhydrous acetone was refluxed on a water-bath for 8 hours. A heavy precipitate of potassium halide began to form soon after the refluxing was started. After cooling, ice was added and the acetone was distilled off. The oily layer was extracted with ether. The ether layer was washed with 5% caustic soda solution several times, then with distilled water and dried over freshly fused potassium carbonate. The ether was then removed by distillation and the residual oil distilled under reduced pressure (Table III).

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